

Development of Tea industry in Darjeeling District: A Study on its area, production and marketing system

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Abstract

India is the second largest producer of tea in the world. It is the largest industry in North Bengal. The present study gives an account of the tea industry of North Bengal. The main objective of the study is to find out the development of tea industry in this part of India with emphasis on its area, production and marketing system. For carrying out the present study a systematic methodology was adopted. To have knowledge of development a picture of history of tea gardens in Darjeeling has been represented. To present the present status of the tea industry the production of tea over the years, its marketing scenario including export and auction status have been highlighted with statistical data. Problems of the tea industry have also been represented in the study. The findings of the present study show that in spite of having rich potentiality and fragrance of tea, the tea industry is not getting good international market. The study also shows that due to some regional political movements the tea industry is facing problems.

Keywords: History, present status, Indian scenario, marketing, problems

Introduction

The economy of North Bengal region is based on three T-s such as Tea, Tourism and Timber. The oldest and the most established industry in the North Bengal region is the tea industry. The tea industry of the region is not only a major factor in the economic stability of the region; it also plays a major role in contributing towards the environment and the society. Large acres of tea plantations provides much needed greenery to maintain the ecological balance of the region, and at the same time it increases the aesthetic value of the landscapes. Tea industry has also the potential to encompass the tourism industry, and already such a plan is being formulated to create a package called 'Tea Tourism'. Tea garden areas not only provide magnificent landscapes; visitors can also get a glimpse of the different cultures, traditions and customs of the many ethnic races populating the tea garden areas.

History of Tea Plantation in Darjeeling

Tea plantations were started in Darjeeling by the British rulers early in the 19th century. In 1815, the growth of an Indigenous tea bush in Assam from which the Singpo hill tribes used to make drink was noticed by a traveller. 'The names of Mr. C. A. Bruce, Cap.Charlton and Maj.Robert Bruce are associated with the discovery of tea plant in Assam. A committee was appointed by Lord Bentinck-the then Governor General of India in 1834 to study a plan for accomplishment of the introduction of tea culture in India and for the superintendence of its execution' (Debnath & Bhattacharjee et.al. 2008:153).The establishment of the tea industry in India was to a great extent, due to the appointment of that committee. The govt. was so impressed with the committee's report that they sent a scientific commission to Assam to report on the indigenous plant and also about the most suitable place for growing it. The first sample of manufactured tea in Assam was ready in 1837. In the year 1838 the first shipment of Indian tea was sent to UK. The shipment consisted of 8

chests of tea. Inspired by the success of tea plantation in Assam, the British took necessary steps for experimental growth of tea in the Darjeeling region.

The establishment of the tea industry in Darjeeling is due to the enterprise of Dr. Campbell, who was appointed Superintendent of Darjeeling at a time when attention was being attracted to the possibility of starting and developing the cultivation and manufacture of tea in the territories under the East India Company. In 1840 Dr. Campbell was transferred from Kathmandu to Darjeeling, and there started the experimental growth of tea (O'Malley, 1907). 'In 1852 Mr. Jackson remarked in a report that the bushes of both Assam and China types were doing well in the garden of the Superintendent, Dr. Campbell, in Darjeeling, as well as in the more extensive plantations of Dr. Withecombe, the Civil Surgeon, and of Major Crommelin, of the Engineers, in a lower valley called Lebong' (Dash, 2011:113).

These plantations appear to have been merely experimental plots, but by the year 1856 the tea plantations began to develop on an extensive and commercial scale. These gardens were set up on the lower slopes since Dr. Hooker believed that the elevation of Darjeeling was too high for the plant to be very productive. Thus since that year the tea gardens came into existence in the district (Table-1).

Gardens like Makaibari, Pandam and Steinthal were also opened at this early period. All these estates are situated in the hills, but about this time the planters began to turn their attention to the Terai, where experimental plantations had already been started. Thus, 'in 1862, the first tea garden opened out at Champta, near the Khaprail by Mr. James White who already planted out the Singel estate near Kurseong' (O'Malley, 1907: 74). However by the end of 1866 more gardens had been opened out in the Terai. In 1875 two gardens were established in Pulbari and Bagrakote. Since that period the cultivation of tea began to spread in Jalpaiguri district.

Table-1: First Tea Gardens of the Darjeeling district

Year of establishment	Areas	Name of the Company/ person
1856	Alubari Lebong spur	Kurseong and Darjeeling Tea Company Darjeeling Land Mortgage Bank
1859	Dhutaria	Dr. Brougham
1860- 1864	Ging, Ambutia, Takdah, Phubsering Takvar and Badamtam	Darjeeling Tea Company Lebong Tea Company

There had been a rapid development of the tea gardens in the hills as the suitability of the soil and climate became apparent. Government offered land to investors on favourable terms and by the end of 1866 there were 39 gardens in production with 10,000 acres under cultivation. In 1870 there were 56 gardens with 11,000 acres under cultivation employing 8,000 labourers. The subsequent development of tea gardens after 1870 can be seen from the table-2.

Table- 2: Tea Gardens in Darjeeling district Darjeeling from the period of 1864 to 1940

Year	No. of gardens	Area under tea in acres
1864	113	18,888
1885	175	38,499
1895	186	48,692
1905	148	50,618
1910	148	51,281
1915	148	54,024
1920	148	59,356
1925	148	59,356
1930	148	59,356
1935	148	59,356
1940	142	63,059

Source: Dash, A J (2011) p.11

Table- 3: Distribution of Tea Gardens in district in 1940

Thana	Number of Tea estates
Darjeeling	19
Jorebunglow	16
Sukhiapokri	9
Pulbazar	2
Rangli Rangliot	9
Kurseong	25
Mirik	5
Siliguri	27
Kharibari	11
Phansidewa	13
Kalimpong	0
Gorubathan	6
Total	142

Source: Dash, A J (2011) p.114

Since 1940 the tea production has increased considerably in spite of difficulties with transportation and costs. In 1942 the output was 26,478,500 lbs. of black tea and 1,242,000 lbs. of green tea. In 1943 the production of black tea and green tea was 25,593,000 lbs and 2,572,500 lbs respectively (Dash, 2011). The labour force employed in the tea industry in 1921 was 44,279 and in 1940 it was 61,540.

Present Status of Tea Industry

World scenario

Tea industry is concentrated mainly in some Asian and African countries. In 2006, world tea production was 3579.79 million kgs. annually. In 2010, world tea production reached over 4066.60 million kgs. The largest producers of tea are the People's Republic of China, India, Kenya, Sri Lanka, and Turkey. India is world's second largest producer (2010) after China. Table-4 shows the amount of tea production by leading countries in recent years.

Table-4: Global Tea Production (Figs. In M.Kgs) by Leading Countries in different Years

Country	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010
China	1028.06	1140.00	1257.60	1358.64	1370.00
India	981.81	986.43	980.82	979.00	966.40
Kenya	310.58	369.61	345.82	314.20	399.01
Sri Lanka	310.82	304.61	318.70	289.78	329.38
Vietnam	142.50	148.27	166.38	154.00	157.00
Turkey	142.00	178.00	155.00	153.00	148.00
Indonesia	146.85	137.25	137.50	136.48	129.20
Bangladesh	53.41	58.42	58.66	60.00	59.17
Malawi	45.01	48.14	41.64	52.56	51.59
Uganda	36.73	44.91	42.75	50.98	56.65
Tanzania	31.35	34.86	31.61	32.09	31.65
Others	350.67	345.58	328.31	351.25	368.55
Total	3579.79	3796.08	3864.79	3931.98	4066.60

Source : Tea Board of India (2010)

Indian scenario

India is the second largest producer of tea in the world (2010). The major tea growing states of India are Assam, West Bengal, Tamil Nadu and Kerala. The other states where tea is grown, to a small extent, are Tripura, Himachal Pradesh, Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, and Karnataka. Recently some of the non-traditional states like Arunachal Pradesh, Manipur, Nagaland, Orissa, and Sikkim have taken up the tea cultivation. The tea production takes place in both large plantations and smaller gardens. However, from the table-5 it is seen that the production of tea is higher in the North India than the South India. The percentage increase of tea production from 2002 to 2008 was 118.69% in North India while it was 47.99% in South India. The overall all India percentage increase was 166.68% during the same period (Table-5).

Tea Production in Darjeeling

The cultivation and production of tea in West Bengal mainly concentrated in Darjiling and Jalpaiguri districts. Tista river demarcates the North Bengal plains into two parts. The western part of the Tista river is known as Terai while the eastern part as Dooars. Tea production in Terai region mostly concentrated in Siliguri
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Subdivision of Darjiling district. However, there are some big and small tea gardens also spread in Uttar Dinajpur. Dooars region mainly covers eastern part of Tista river which includes the entire Jalpaiguri district of West Bengal and only one tea garden of Koch Bihar district. However the tea growing areas of Darjiling comprises of Darjiling Sadar and Kurseong, some parts of Kalimpong subdivision.

Table- 5: Production of Tea in India (Quantity in Million Kgs.)

Year	North India	South India	Total
2002	631.75	206.72	838.47
2003	648.28	229.85	878.13
2004	662.19	230.78	892.97
2005	718.42	227.55	945.97
2006	753.24	228.56	981.80
2007	764.74	221.69	986.43
2008	733.92	246.90	980.82
Percentage increase from 2002 to 2008	118.69%	47.99%	166.68%

Source : Various issues of Tea Statistics

From the Table 6 it is found that in 2001 there were 1554 tea estates in West Bengal. The number of estates increased due to the rapid expansion of small tea holdings after 90s. The expansion of small tea gardens mainly concentrated on Terai and Dooars Regions. In Terai region the total number of estates rose from 92 to 921 and in Dooars region it has rose from 168 to 548 due to tremendous expansion of small tea holdings during that period. Tea plantation of Terai is mainly centred in Siliguri Subdivision of Darjiling district and few gardens in North Dinajpur district. The Darjeeling tea has its own special aroma, that rare fragrance that fills the senses. Tea from Darjeeling has been savoured by connoisseurs all over the world. Like all luxury brands Darjeeling Tea is aspired to, worldwide. This Tea cannot be grown or manufactured anywhere else in the world. Just as Champagne is indigenous to the Champagne district of France, so is Darjeeling Tea to Darjeeling. The crafting of Darjeeling Tea begins in the field. Where women workers begin plucking early in the morning, when the leaves are still covered with dew. The spirals of walking women gradually twist, then unfold to form a line. The tea is picked fresh every day, as fresh as the crisp green leaves can make them. The tea bushes are mystic messages on the Earth's canvas.

Tea is Darjeeling's most famous export. It produces the bulk of West Bengal's crop, which is almost a quarter of India's total. The tea from some of these estates is of very high quality. The world record for the highest price paid for tea is held by some fine leaves from the Castleton Estate in Darjeeling, for which a Japanese bidder paid US\$220 per kg. Table-7 shows the number of tea estates in Darjeeling district over the years.

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Table 6: Number of Tea Estates in North Bengal

Area	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001
Darjiling	83	80	80	85	85	85	85
Dooars	168	191	191	423	532	545	548
Terai	92	182	182	607	834	910	921
West Bengal	343	453	453	1115	1451	1540	1554

Source : Tea Board of India 2010)

Table 7: Tea estates in Darjeeling district

Year	No of Tea Garden
2001-02	115
2002-03	100
2003-04	100
2004-05	97
2005-06	97

Table-8 shows that the Darjeeling region ranks third position in the production of tea in West Bengal. In 2001 the production of tea was 9841 thousand kgs (5.27% of the total West Bengal tea production) and it has been increased by 11586 thousand kgs (4.97% of the total West Bengal tea production) in 2008.

Sources: Darjeeling Planters Association, Darjeeling

Tarai Tea Association, Siliguri

Table-8: Production of Tea in Darjeeling and other major areas of North Bengal (Figures in Thousand kgs.)

Areas	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008
Darjeeling	9841	9180	9582	10065	11312	10854	10007	11586
Terai	49388	53606	59786	69239	77078	87064	87502	79517
Dooars	127611	125235	131267	135237	129156	139188	138835	142030
Total West Bengal	186840	188021	200635	214541	217546	237106	236344	233133

Source : ITC Annual Bulletin Supplement (2011)

Tea Marketing Scenario

Tea is one of the most refreshing and popular beverages of the world. The world tea marketing scenario shows that Kenya ranks first (441.02 million kgs) in the export of tea followed by China (302.42 million kgs) and Sri Lanka (258.59 million kgs) in 2010. India's position is fourth (193.29 million kgs). One striking feature is that India ranks in second position in the production of tea in the world but it ranks fourth position in the export of tea. The main reason is that India has a large internal market of tea. A large portion of population drinks tea.

Table- 9: World Export of Tea (in M.Kgs)

Country	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010
Kenya	312.16	343.70	383.44	342.48	441.02
China	286.59	289.43	296.94	302.95	302.42
Sri Lanka	314.92	294.25	298.82	279.84	298.59
India	218.73	178.75	203.12	197.90	193.29
Vietnam	105.12	110.93	104.00	95.00	98.00
Indonesia	95.34	83.66	96.21	92.30	87.10
Argentina	70.72	74.88	77.23	69.19	101.00
Malawi	41.96	46.59	40.07	46.55	48.58
Uganda	32.70	-	-	-	-
Tanzania	24.13	29.13	24.77	21.51	25.39
Zimbabwe	11.38	7.60	5.65	7.54	8.50
Bangladesh	4.79	10.56	8.39	3.15	0.91
Others	63.09	69.14	75.08	76.62	77.64
Total	1581.63	1582.26	1656.11	1582.95	1733.27

Source : ITC Annual Bulletin Supplement (2010)

India is one of the largest Tea producer, exporter and consumer in the world. Indian tea is the finest quality in the world. It is being cultivated in the high ranges of Northern and Southern India and the best quality tea are CTC and Orthodox Assam Tea. The consumption is above 600 Million kgs per year. The market consists of both Leaf and Dust Teas both in the CTC and Orthodox Grades.

The marketing of tea is different from other agricultural commodities. Producers have various marketing channels to sell their produce. The main two marketing channels are (a) Private sale, and (b) Auction sale. Private sale can be further classified into two sectors, (1) Ex-garden sale, and (2) Forward contracts.

The ex-garden sale is the sale under taken at the garden level immediately after the manufactured tea is released from the factory. The manufactured tea is brought both by domestic and foreign buyers from the different gardens. Through forward contracts, the concerned buyers and sellers draw up a contract regarding the amount, terms and transactions before the tea crop is ready for sale; then transaction takes place immediately after being manufactured.

Tea is also sold through Six Auction centres situated in different places of India. North Bengal tea accounts for about 25 per cent of total tea production of India and is equivalent to the total South India production. The market of North Bengal teas are the Siliguri and Kolkata auctions. The producers of North Bengal send their teas to Siliguri and Kolkata for their disposal. Though auction is the most important channel to sell tea all over the world, but in India sales through auction

markets is extremely low and marketing through ex-garden sales and private sales has assumed importance. The private sale has increased by around 50 per cent in case of Dooars and Darjiling and 35 to 40 per cent in Terai. Therefore only 50 to 60 per cent teas of North Bengal actually sold through auction markets. Table-11 shows the auction scenario of Darjeeling, Kolkata and Siliguri from 2010 to 2011 (January to April).

Table- 10: Exports of Tea from India

FINANCIAL YEAR	North India		South India		All India	
	Qty (M.Kgs.)	Value (Rs.Crs.)	Qty (M.Kgs.)	Value (Rs.Crs.)	Qty (M.Kgs.)	Value(Rs.Crs.)
2004-2005	101.47	1228.70	104.34	696.01	205.81	1924.71
2005-2006	100.53	1160.14	96.14	633.44	196.67	1793.58
2006-2007	100.87	1223.20	117.28	822.52	218.15	2045.72
2007-2008	110.15	1291.18	75.17	597.50	185.32	1888.68
2008-2009	106.30	1560.96	84.34	820.83	190.64	2381.79

Source: Tea Board of India (2010)

Table-11: Auction of Darjeeling and other areas' Tea from 2010 to 2011 (January to April)

Region	2010(Million kgs)	2011(Million kgs)	Differences
Kolkata	37.1	36.8	0.3
Siliguri	19.1	21.1	2
Darjeeling	0.54	0.37	.17

Source: Tea Board of India (2010)

All teas produced in the tea growing areas of India, including Darjeeling, are administered by the Tea Board, India under the Tea Act, 1953. Since its establishment, the Tea Board has had sole control over the growing and exporting of Darjeeling Tea and it is this which has given rise to the reputation enjoyed by Darjeeling Tea. The Tea Board has been engaged in the protection and preservation of this treasured icon of India's cultural heritage as a Geographical Indication on a worldwide basis.

To assist the Tea Board in its role of authenticating regional origin of Darjeeling Tea, it has developed a unique logo, known as the Darjeeling logo. Use of the Darjeeling word and logo are protected as Geographical Indications in India and as Certification Trade Marks in UK, USA and India.

The Darjeeling logo is registered in Belgium, Netherlands, Luxembourg, Germany, Austria, Spain, France, *Journal of Geo-Environment Observer, Vol.1, No. 2*

Portugal, Italy, Switzerland, (former) Yugoslavia, Egypt and Lebanon as a collective mark, in Canada as an official mark and as a trademark in Japan and Russia. The DARJEELING word is also registered as a trademark in Russia. Tea Board has registered the Darjeeling word as a certification mark in Australia, as a community collective mark in the EU and as a collective mark in Germany and Japan.

Problems

In recent times the production of Darjeeling tea has been declined. Production is set to be lower in 2010 by at least 10% which has impacted supplies to export markets of Japan, Germany and the UK. The Darjeeling tea industry, which reported a 12% lower crop between January and August this year, may end up with a production of less than 8 million kg. The crop was affected during the first flush due to drought. Even the second-flush production was affected due to erratic weather conditions. At times, it has been difficult for the exporters to meet the export commitment due to the shortage. It has been a bad year for the industry. However, the only silver lining was a steady domestic demand. Surprisingly, the domestic demand for the Darjeeling tea has gone up by 30% which generally doesn't happen. But the domestic price cannot match the international prices that Darjeeling planters fetch.

The problem was triggered by a severe drought which started in October 2009 and continued till April 2010, when leaves dropped. As a result of this, the first-flush tea, which comes around mid-May and contributes about 20% of the crop, was down by about 35%. Even though prices firmed up due to a shortfall, producers failed to benefit because of low production. However, the surge in domestic demand has brought much cheer for the industry. There are 87 tea estates in Darjeeling, all of which are running now. However, bad weather was not the only reason behind the crop loss. Shifting to organic methods of production has also led to a less output. During 2010, as many as 35 Darjeeling gardens changed hands with some crops being lost in the transformation. The movement of Gorkha Janamukti Morcha also responsible for such low production.

Despite the development of auction centres nearby tea producing areas in India as well as in North Bengal, private sale of made tea still dominates and occupies a big share in the total tea sale. Generally good quality tea is directly sold to the buyers through ex-garden or forward contract. The ratio of auction and private sale has been 60:40 for the last few years. A major portion of made tea is being marketed through the private sale in domestic market and to the foreign buyers. Ex-garden sales have some serious disadvantages and ex-garden sales are not registered anywhere for quantity or price, and therefore do not come into the mainstream of information.

In the most auction markets in India a major percentage of tea bid in the auctions was brought by a small number of managing agency houses. So far as the concerned existing auction centres in India, Siliguri auction centre has failed to create a competitive atmosphere within the buyers. Another important problem of Siliguri tea auction centre is that the majority of tea trading communities in these areas do not have any family tradition to run the tea estates. Their main intention is to earn quick profits without any consideration for the development of the tea auction centre (Sarker, 1972). Tea Marketing Control Order Report (2203) and Sen Committee Report (2004) gave more emphasis on larger sale of tea through auction. Therefore these drawbacks of the tea industry should be removed with judicious steps for the better economic development of the region.

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